

TECHNO-POLITICS: A CONVERSATION WITH BERNARD CACHE

Bernard Cache is among those who have most rigorously examined the promises—and limitations—of digital technologies in architecture. Yet, despite his credentials, it is difficult to imagine a more ironic beginning to our conversation about enabling technologies than watching them fail. We spent nearly half an hour attempting, and failing, to establish a video connection. The cause of this technical glitch remains unclear. Nevertheless, it is a fitting prelude.

Trained across architecture, economics, and philosophy—most notably under the guidance of Gilles Deleuze—Cache has consistently woven together theory, computation, and non-standard modes of production. He anticipated the architectural consequences of CAD/CAM technologies and articulated the concept of the objectile: an architectural object understood not as a fixed form, but as a “continuum through variation,” a field of potential transformations: an idea that continues to shape contemporary digital practice.

Cache asks that we speak only of Desargues, Pascal, and projective geometry—historical figures and conceptual frameworks to which we will indeed return. Still, I cannot resist asking what he is currently working on, and what occupies his thinking today.

BERNARD CACHE: I am still working on topics related to projective geometry, and I am currently supervising two PhD students whose research overlaps with my own and focuses on the use of open-source software—specifically Speckle, developed by the Romanian architect Dimitri Stefanescu. Speckle’s initial aim is to develop an application that enables real-time exchange within architectural practice.

MARCO VANUCCI: The *open source* is, first of all, a political issue.

BC: Yes, I emphasize this because I believe open source is a central issue today. Not only in an ideological sense, but in a very concrete political one: it directly affects the everyday life of architects and architectural offices. If, for any reason, a studio cannot afford commercial software licenses, it may not even be able to view its own work. This is extremely serious. It means that you do not truly own what you produce. We need to respond to this state of affairs.

MV: In your most recent writings, a very critical stance emerges toward the way in which digital technology has permeated our lives. Yet, the enthusiasm with which you and other pioneers of parametric design embraced computer-aided design and manufacturing was grounded in the context of a new world order characterized by open markets and the free movement of goods, people, and information. A world in which the neoliberal project seemed to have delivered the “end of history” and, with it, thanks to the development of digital technology, new extraordinary possibilities to design a different society, free from the limitations of one-size-fit-all ideologies.

Today, that project is in crisis: the world is marked by protectionism, sovereigntism, and autocracies: digital technologies, instead of uniting us, have contributed to dividing society. How do you experience this change?

BC: My position today is one of retreat within the folds of history in order to change the future. More precisely, I am looking at things that were about to appear in the past but did not. The idea is that, with a broader past, by actualizing things that remained virtual, we might have a better future. Otherwise, I am deeply pessimistic about the future: I believe we are heading toward a stalemate. I would recommend reading *Sans transition* by Jean-Baptiste Fressoz,¹ which shows that there has never been a true “energy transition,” since technological systems have always been deeply intertwined. It is an illusion to believe that we can simply abandon unsustainable or obsolete energy sources.

Reversing course is extremely difficult. When I worked on digital technologies, I operated within a structured professional environment grounded in mathematics, rules, and syntax. I could not have imagined that speaking to one’s children or paying taxes would one day require the use of extremely expensive—and often poorly designed—digital tools.

¹ F. M. Clarke, D. E. Smith, “‘Essay pour les Coniques’ of Blaise Pascal,” *Isis*, 10, 1, 1928, pp. 16–20.

Today, it is almost impossible to participate fully in social life without owning a device that costs between 500 and 1,000 euros. These technologies exclude the poor, the elderly, people with disabilities, and those who are digitally illiterate. We are creating a new form of illiteracy. One day, I would like to work on a public digital terminal—standardized, affordable, and based on a minimal shared syntax. The first step would be to introduce mandatory public standards for the user interfaces of all services of public interest—for example, by requiring a single, universal command that allows users to return to a neutral point² in any application. The second step would be to build consensus around a basic, low-cost, sustainable terminal for every citizen, since we can no longer function as human beings without such devices. This terminal should then be produced locally, at least on a European scale, while also involving collaboration with developing countries.

MV: The first issue, then, is not only technological but syntactic.

BC: Exactly. I insist on the word *syntax*. The problem of false truths is not only a matter of content; it is also a matter of syntax. We opened digital technology to the world without providing the structures needed to make it intelligible. From Tamagotchi to Facebook, entry into the digital realm has been widespread but unstructured. Today, no one wants to write code anymore; no one wants to think about graphical syntax. And yet, it is syntax that makes truth possible. This problem is in fact deeply rooted in our history. Even in mathematics, geometric figures have always been considered secondary relative to the text, which means, for instance, that a figure could be drawn symmetrically even though the theorem relied on an arbitrary configuration, not restricted to a symmetrical one. As Mario Carpo³ has emphasized very well, images were always neglected in classical culture, and then, were treated as if they were no graphical syntax.

MV: You are referring to the pervasiveness of digital technology in everyday life.

BC: Yes. Even more than a political issue, this pervasiveness has become an anthropological one, just as in geology we now have to speak of the

² A neutral point means a state in which the software is not engaged in any command or action.

³ M. Carpo, *Architecture in the Age of Printing*, The MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, 2001.

Anthropocene due to the pervasiveness of our technological impact on nature. This anthropological pervasiveness of our minds and bodies is such that, for example, when I go to the mountains, I find myself among the few who hike without wearing a watch that tracks their heart rate. It is astonishing. Today, in Switzerland, there are people who cycle through the Canton of Vaud while tracing the borders of the entire country on their GPS, all within the same region. They call it a work of art. But the artwork is the route, not the digital experience. What truly concerns them is the digital object.

I never imagined that digital technology would penetrate every aspect of life so deeply.

MV: This concern about the “tyranny of the algorithm” is not new. Architect Luigi Moretti, the father of parametric design, already in the 1970s, shortly before his death, warned against extending algorithmic logic outside controlled disciplinary contexts. He said it could not be indiscriminately scaled to all aspects of life.

BC: That is true, and we can see it clearly today. In France, for example, there is debate about the use of mobile phones in schools. A device that scrambles signals would be enough, and could be switched on and off at will, according to an appropriate time schedule: students would still have their phones in the classroom, but could not use them when it is inappropriate. In case of an emergency, they could use a landline, just as in the past.

MV: So, school as a protected space, a place free from the invasiveness of digital devices.

BC: Exactly. It is troubling that we can no longer imagine society as having technology-free spaces—places where there is no digital communication, only communication between people, or silence. School should be one of those spaces. This is not a reactionary argument; it concerns the very possibility of autonomy. How can a child become autonomous if they are constantly tracked, reachable, and controlled?

MV: Ultimately, the broader outcome of the digital revolution has been precisely this possibility of redesigning an atomized, granular society, made possible by economies without scale. This has led to extreme individualism. Everyone has their own device, their own “scale.”

BC: Yes, individualism and isolation. The beginning of this conversation (with the problem with the camera) was perfect, in the most perverse sense. What surprises me is that Europe does not respond with its own tools. Why do we not have European open-source software for communicating among ourselves? Why did the LiMux⁴ project, which proposed open-source software for the public administration of Munich and a few other cities, fail? Why did Paris not join the project? Why do public administration not provide their employees with Fairphones⁵ for professional use. Why does the French army grant contracts to Microsoft without making serious bids? Why has the French school administration just renewed its contract with Microsoft while the government claims to be looking for independent solutions? European servility amazes me. Europe could form new alliances, for example with the Maghreb and the Mashreq. We have enormous intellectual resources in Algeria, Egypt, and other neighboring countries. But you need to establish the rules of the game. Without syntax, nothing can be built.

MV: Back to syntax. What exactly do you mean?

BC: The fact that there are public, shared, slowly evolving rules around which consensus can be created. Syntax is a stable reference. Take Wikipedia. It is one of the few large successful projects in the digital world. I use it a lot and support the project financially. But recently, when I tried to donate, I could not find “Switzerland” in its place in the alphabetical list of countries. There are also elementary lexical considerations: we should not use words that are not in the dictionary unless there are sound reasons to do so.

MV: So syntax can be understood as the foundation of truth.

BC: Exactly. Without syntax, there is no truth. Truth is even more a question of syntax than of content. And when syntax has to evolve, the evolution should be done in continuity. No open-source strategy can succeed without institutional continuity and support. Young, brilliant software developers can invent whatever they want, but some institutions must support them: universities, the state. Otherwise, everything is lost when the developers abandon their task. This is a fundamental political issue.

⁴ See: “LiMux,” Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/LiMux>, (accessed 2 March 2026).

⁵ Fairphone, <https://shop.fairphone.com/fr>, (accessed 2 March 2026).

Actually, this is the support that universities such as Stanford have provided to computer and software companies since the beginning of the digital age.

MV: Your path over the years has led you to study Vitruvius, Dürer, Pascal, Leibniz, and Desargues. Why this attention to the past?

BC: Because I've heard people, even well-intentioned ones, like Paul Virilio, say that we live in a "non-Euclidean" world. These are violent slogans. All rationality comes from Euclid. Even non-Euclidean geometries are variants of Euclidean geometry. When Descartes introduced algebra, he was still thinking geometrically, imagining shapes when writing equations. There was continuity.⁶ People who cut the links with fundamental fields such as Euclidean geometry are just shrinking the past and endangering our present and future.

MV: And today, this historical awareness is missing.

BC: Yes. In many engineering schools there are no longer consistent courses in the history of mathematics. Yet the tradition continues. Andrea Del Centina, a great Italian historian of geometry, wrote a fundamental book: *From Here to Infinity: Tracing the Origin and Development of Projective Geometry*.⁷ It is my daily bible. I keep it beside me every day.

MV: So geometry, formal logic as a gateway to other forms of knowledge. Yet, today we can say many things about architecture—from parametric to artificial intelligence—but it is clear that the formal expression of design has lost centrality. Is that not so? And why?

BC: Yes, and rightly so. Because the problem—apart from the far right, immigration, and digital technology—is climate change. People do not realize the urgency. Here in Switzerland, we are already more than 2°C above the pre-industrial average temperature. Let us say we have thirty years left, after which it is the end. Some discussions are truly urgent. For instance, whatever happens in Iran nowadays, this country will remain with summers reaching 50°C, and two thirds of the population lacking water. And guess who is responsible for that?

⁶ H. J. M. Bos, *Redefining Geometrical Exactness: Descartes' Transformation of the Early Modern Concept of Construction*, Springer, New York, 2001.

⁷ A. Del Centina, A. Gimigliano, *From Here to Infinity: Tracing the Origin and Development of Projective Geometry*, Springer, Cham, 2025.

We are restituting, in the guise of heath, the oil that the British had stolen to the Iranians. This oil, reappropriated by Mosaddegh in 1951, was stolen a second time in 1953 by the americans with the complacency of the Shah. And now they are considering his son as a convenient solution to the problems they created.

This is why the architectural problem is no longer fancy design: the issue is data management and sustainable processes of production, construction, maintenance and, of course, habitability. It is so complex that perhaps it could be a challenge for AI.

So, my research is not anymore focused on formal expression, as it was naively in the 1990s. Instead, I am trying to reconnect links that were never articulated.

MV: Yet, you insist on studying the axioms and constructions of projective geometry, a field in which the formal logic of mathematics encodes epistemological and philosophical assumptions. You have remarked that, since the mid-eighteenth century—since Kant, “the first philosopher who had nothing to say about mathematics”—a “harmful legacy has persisted, separating philosophy from mathematics.” Is it this unity between the sciences and the humanities that, in some ways, you are trying to reconnect?

BC: Projective geometry is a good example of things in the past that did not happen. To be sure, it developed very well in the field of mathematics, but it did not fulfill its promise of delivering common methods to several practices such as: draughting, stonecutting, or solar clock construction. I will give you a very important example with the concept of the infinite. The common idea is that a line has 2 infinities: one at each of its ends. For a number of reasons, Desargues came up with the idea that a line has only one single point at infinity, which links its two ends. The image of this unique point at infinity is the vanishing point attached to the direction of the line. This uniqueness of the infinite point transforms the line into a cyclic element. It is a key notion of projective geometry, which remains to be fully implemented in CAD software, since it would imply being able to transform translation into rotation, and vice versa.

Nobody knows to what extent an ordinary user of that software would be ready to take that into account, considering that there has been at least one user of projective geometry who understood that perfectly, namely Pascal. But strangely enough, Pascal never tried to implement this uniqueness of the infinite in his philosophical writings.

The same happens with Leibniz, when he says that a monad is a “perspective” on the world. Leibniz stays with the common idea that each individual is a point of view on the universe, without taking advantage of the notion of involution, so central in Desargues’ geometry. My guess is that projective geometry is full of concepts that we can still take advantage of, and interestingly enough, this geometry emerged within the field of architecture.

It is strange and interesting because all this changes our idea of the classical as something boring, already organized, with nothing more to say. I am astonished by the contemporaneity one encounters in the folds of history. Just think of the fact that Desargues only wrote drafts of projects⁸ (*Brouillon de projet*)⁹ or examples.¹⁰ In his *Manière universelle*,¹¹ Abraham Bosse inserted some writings of Desargues, presented as “a notebook like a lost child.”¹²

MV: You seem to be searching, in the folds of history, for traces of the future. History is indeed crucial. It constitutes a fundamental question of our time: on the one hand, the uninterrupted flow of information

⁸ For English readers, a nice introduction to Desargues’ geometry would be: J. V. Field, J. J. Gray, *The Geometrical Work of Girard Desargues*, Springer-Verlag, New York, Berlin, Heidelberg, London, Paris & Tokyo, 1987.

⁹ In geometry, see G. Desargues, *Brouillon project d’une atteinte aux événements des rencontres du cône avec un plan*, Gallica / Bibliothèque nationale de France, <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k105071b.image>, (accessed 2 March 2026). In stereotomy, see G. Desargues, *Brouillon Project d’Exemple d’une manière universelle du S. G. D. L. touchant la pratique du trait à preuves pour la coupe des pierres en l’Architecture: et de l’éclaircissement d’une manière de réduire au petit pied en Perspective comme en Géométral, & de tracer tous Quadrans plats d’heures égales au Soleil*, Paris, 1640. In gnomonics, see G. Desargues, *Brouillon Project du S.G.D.L. touchant une manière universelle de poser le style et tracer les lignes d’un Quadrant aux rayons du Soleil, en quelqu’onque endroit possible, avec la Règle, le Compas, l’équerre et le plomb*, 1640; for the recovered edition, see A. J. Turner, “Another Lost Work by Girard Desargues Recovered,” *Archives Internationales d’Histoire des Sciences*, 34, 1984, pp. 61–67.

¹⁰ In perspective, see G. Desargues, *L’exemple de l’une des manières universelles du Sieur Girard Desargues Lyonnais touchant la pratique de la perspective sans employer aucun tiers point, de distance ny d’autre nature, qui soit hors du champ de l’ouvrage*, Jacques Dugast, Paris, 1636.

¹¹ A. Bosse, *Manière universelle de Mr Desargues, pour pratiquer la perspective par petit-pied, comme le géométral. Ensemble les places et proportions des fortes et foibles touches, teintes ou couleurs*, Pierre Des-Hayes, Paris, 1648, p. 311.

¹² The beginning of the notebook inserted as a lost child: A. Bosse, *Manière universelle de Mr Desargues, pour pratiquer la perspective par petit-pied, comme le géométral. Ensemble les places et proportions des fortes et foibles touches, teintes ou couleurs*, Pierre Des-Hayes, Paris, 1648, p. 335.

encourages historical amnesia; on the other, probabilistic systems linked to big data assume that what happened and has been recorded will recur. Mario Carpo argues that Large Language Models, in fact, automate “creative imitation,” a process central to Western artistic experience, grounded in the idea of art as *mimesis* of reality.

BC: I understand what Mario means, but I would not put it that way. As you say, artificial intelligence is a matter of probability, of common opinion. It takes what exists, makes a probability calculation, and provides the most likely answers. It is what you do when you have no knowledge of a problem. Statistically, it may work many times.

However, for example, one of the greatest experts in the field, Luc Julia (French engineer who invented Apple Siri and is now Chief Technology Officer at Renault) clearly states that the fully autonomous car will very likely never exist. When you take a driverless taxi in San Francisco, there is actually someone in a control room who intervenes when a problem arises. So, this is not knowledge. It is not syntax: it is probability. The question of syntax is fundamental. It is not because we have a lot of information that we have knowledge. People are lost because this information is unstructured.

MV: Somehow, this is also Noam Chomsky’s position: he argues that AI is deficient because it processes language statistically rather than through an innate grammar that’s similar to that of humans. It lacks true understanding and critical thinking, remaining morally indifferent despite ethical safeguards.

BC: Yes, it is precisely a question of grammar, of syntax, and of lexicon. It is the same reason why, in projective geometry—especially in applying perspective—I realized that fundamental elements were not properly named. This is one of the reasons why this geometry never reached the public. *The more information you get, the more you need to organize it. Just remember that one disinformation technique is to submerge your enemy with irrelevant, unstructured information.*

Naming things is extremely important, and the fact that Desargues did not do so is worth discussing, because he was actually very attentive to language. For instance, he did not name the plane parallel to the picture plane passing by the observer. This observer plane intersects the object plane in a line made of points that have as much importance as

Figure 1. Vanishing point on the Vanishing line: the point of convergence of images of parallel object lines. Illustration by Bernard Cache.

Figure 2. Foot point on the Foot line: the point of convergence of object lines having parallel images. Illustration by Bernard Cache.

the vanishing points on the vanishing line. But Desargues did not give them a special name and, as such, those points—which I would call “foot points”—remained unnoticed.

My guess is that there are at least three layers in Desargues’ thought, and that he only disseminated the first because he thought of the others as out of reach of the average draughtsman, stonemason, or builder of solar clocks.

For example, in his first writing on perspective, *L'exemple* (1636),¹³ he dedicates nine pages out of ten to explain the first layer, which amounts to building a coordinate system in the object plane that transforms into another system into the picture plane, together with a reduction scale. Then, in the last page, he writes: “since I have a bit of space left, I will say something for the contemplatives.” And in this single spare page, he explains very important things that amount to making the foot point an equivalent of the vanishing point. Desargues will never come back to this second layer although it provides constructive methods equivalent to those of Apollonius, but extended to general oblique cones rather than limited to circular ones. Actually, this second layer is not so complex, but Desargues was already engaged in the development of his third layer, based on the rather sophisticated concept of involution.¹⁴ Not only does this powerful concept require some deep mathematical understanding but it requires calculations that would repel most practitioners. As a result, Pascal would develop alternative methods based on the theorem which bears his name. Pascal then wrote a whole treatise on conics¹⁵ which, for a number of reasons, was never published. Hence, seventeenth-century projective geometry remains a kind of phantom theory

¹³ G. Desargues, “L'Exemple de l'une des manières universelles,” in *Œuvres de Desargues réunies et analysées*, Leiber, Paris, 1864.

¹⁴ For mathematicians, involution is the ancestor of the 19th century cross ratio. In perspective, all rectangles object * image have constant area, provided you measure them appropriately: a) the measure of the object is its distance to the foot point; b) the measure of the image is its distance to the vanishing point. Since all those rectangles are equal, their corner opposed to the observer’s eye lies on a hyperbola. Desargues starts his major *Brouillon Project ... des Rencontres d'un Cône avec un Plan* by involuting this planar hyperbola into a linear relation on the vanishing radius. The problem is that Desargues does not refer to perspective as his starting consideration. Not only he does not mention that the *stump* of his involution is actually the observer’s eye, but he quickly discards it from his rather complex relations of involution. Hence, his theory of involution is totally abstracted from the perspectival scene. See B. Cache, *The Perspective Block*, forthcoming.

¹⁵ Blaise Pascal, *Conicorum Opus Completum et Conica Apollonii et alia innumera unica fere propositione amplectens*, 1654, which is only known through the notes taken by Leibniz, in particular on the 1st chapter “Generatio conisectionum tangentium et secantium;

that was never fully formulated, although it engages fundamental notions such as representation. Ignoring the involution and the complex topology of the projective plane, art historians such as Erwin Panofsky¹⁶ can discuss at length upon perspective without entering into its intricacies.

Once again, it is a matter of syntax. In mathematics, there are phases of invention, but they must be followed by phases of formalization and organization. Syntax seems to me the most important point, without which we could not fight the far right.

The far right gains traction when there is no order. This is why Trump attacks universities: because universities are the places where knowledge is built, given order and meaning.

MV: I fear, however, that despite good intentions, these are topics that risk being somewhat impenetrable. In architecture, for example, computational design has ended up alienating many architects who, in reaction, retreated into the status quo or the tradition.

BC: We must not go backward. We must organize. And we must take autonomy. My argument is not about returning to candles.

MV: On the contrary, your position sounds more like a call to arms: that is, a call to shift the discussion to a political plane through the development of open-source software and platforms. However, it could be seen as an extension beyond disciplinary boundaries.

BC: I think open source is needed and it requires institutional support: a European digital autonomy that would collaborate with North Africa, where there are excellent engineers and intellectual resources. And then organization, and also having spaces where there is no more digital: setting limits, a sense of boundary that goes together with syntax.

Another project to work on is the digitalization of public administration: every citizen should have access to a basic digital terminal to perform essential state services (taxes, healthcare, banking, etc.). A service that only allows checking bank balance, doing postal services, and normal tasks of a modern citizen.

seu projectio peripheriae, tangentium et secantium circuli, in quibuscumque oculi, plani ac tabellae positionibus.”

¹⁶ E. Panofsky, *Perspective as Symbolic Form* [1924], trans. C. S. Wood, Zone Books, New York, 1991.

Then there is the issue of mobility. The electric car makes no sense for someone like me, who lives in a city with the metro and good public transport. But I was born in the countryside, and I know perfectly well that, when you are in the fields, you need a car for the last mile. I think of intelligent and public cars. They could be public vehicles, not privately owned, for which the state grants concessions fostering competition: these fleets of cars should operate permanently and should be locally controlled. This would be a leftist approach to electric cars, as opposed to the electric private SUV. What I mean is that there is room for action: digital technologies have become what they are today because boundaries were not set, and large American corporations were allowed to develop them out of control.

MV: For years, the focus was on experimenting with new possibilities offered by new numerically controlled production tools: CAD/CAM, file-to-production, parametric design, etc. These technologies afforded the possibility to design complex forms, and so complex forms were designed just because it was finally possible to do so. Today, however, it is urgent to understand what kind of society we want to build. What you call syntax, in other words, the problem of understanding the meaning of our technological world order.

BC: Today, we must “tame the beast.” I repeat: the fact that parents oppose a device that blocks children’s communications in schools is a very important symptom. Yet those same parents agree to surveillance that checks all students’ backpacks at the school entrance: they prefer actual police-style control (!) rather than a radical, clear, and simple solution: signal scramblers switched on and off at appropriate time. This is an architectural issue: defining limits, walls within which communication occurs only when it makes sense. We must think of a digital architecture with disconnected enclosures.

MV: Speaking of architecture, I recall a wonderful lecture you gave at the Architectural Association, in which, speaking of the Tower of the Winds by Andronikos of Cyrrhus in Athens, you discussed how, at the origins of Western architecture, we do not find a refuge, but a machine to measure (time, sun, wind). And again: your interest in Vitruvius lies in his work on the design of war machines. How does the concept of the *machine de guerre* inform your architectural thinking and your view of architecture

as a calculating tool? Do you still think of architecture as *machinatio*, of being a tool for measuring and computing reality?

BC: Today, in architecture, I am mainly focused on the software aspect. Beside projective geometry, which still has to be fully implemented within CAD software, I am supporting the work of two of my PhD students: Ahmed Waël and Raphael Vouilloz, who are developing a Speckle viewer enabling a better understanding of geometrical construction. Speckle is a startup that is developing an application allowing one not to be trapped in a single software but, on the contrary, to connect different software platforms. This is fundamental, and it is what underlies open source.

As for the city, I think the fundamental problem is climate change. I remember a friend in Rome, five or six years ago, telling me that it was already 30°C at the end of May. Now in France, we are almost there. The speed of this phenomenon is incredible.

So yes, definitely, we should build with timber, with CNC machines, etc. But I have never seen a precise analysis of the climatic implications of these systems.

The book I mentioned earlier, *Sans transition*, shows how energies are interdependent and that you cannot easily switch from one system to another: when coal arrived, people used less wood for heating, but to go into the mines, wooden beams were needed, so wood consumption actually increased. Therefore, without wood you cannot have coal, and without coal, you cannot have steel or cement, etc. Beyond the slogans of some politicians, implementing an “ecological transition” is much more difficult than people think. Perhaps artificial intelligence can help, because the problem is very complex.

MV: So do you really think it is only a matter of software? What about hardware? What role does built architecture play?

BC: In the end, we still need to produce wooden houses. I am still involved in this project through collaboration with TopSolid: not yet at the scale of the entire house, but in furniture and soon in carpentry. Prefabrication and the organization of production are making progress. It is important not to abandon them. Just as we need oil to build solar panels. But understanding whether we are moving toward good or bad outcomes is very difficult.

MV: So we need a new mathematical, technological humanism.

BC: Politically, yes.

MV: Forgive me for the digression, but I think it somehow relates to what we are discussing: on one hand, technology frightens us; on the other, it promises salvation, omniscience, total computation—there is, in short, a mystical aura surrounding the salvific power of technology. Even Pascal, in the *mystical hexagram* linked to the study of conics, glimpsed the possibility of a transcendent meaning.

BC: Hm, what was called the mystical hexagram is actually the unique theorem¹⁷ upon which Pascal built the 400 propositions of his full treatise on conics, precisely in order to bypass the complexity of Desargues' involution. Yet I am very suspicious of everything called *mystical*. Religion is certainly what prevented Pascal to take full advantage of the unicity of the infinite within his philosophical writings although it could have been a nice theological concept.

But yes, today it is up to us to save ourselves. We have to develop technology and guide it. If we use it without political control—which is what is happening now—it will be our catastrophe.

We must find a way to organize technology by engaging in the solution of practical problems. For example: how to organize digital communication in schools?

When I say we must prevent any communication via cell phones, it does not mean there should be no computers to learn coding or to organize one's digital space, and even to teach smart uses of cell phones. Let us be clear: my position is not anti-technology.

You began by saying we could not have imagined the situation we are in, and that is true. But we should take the syntax we had in a highly organized professional field and bring it to the political field of common digital life.

MV: It is very clear: a plea for a new digital sovereignty.

¹⁷ Pascal's theorem has it that any hexagon inscribed into a conic has the three intersection points of its three pairs of opposed sides aligned on a straight line. In the particular case where the hexagon becomes regular, those three intersection points are the unique point at infinity of the three directions of its sides, lying on the unique line at infinity of the plane.

BC: Yes. I think that, in a few years, between Trump, Putin, Xi Jinping, and the climate crisis, if we do nothing, our human species will just disappear.

MV: In architecture, there is this tendency toward technocratic “solutionism.” The risk is developing research that is unguided and generic. Take the last Venice Biennale: there are good projects, animated by good intentions, but too often without a political or humanistic vision.

BC: And above all, without planning. We need to return to planning.

MV: Planning is another major theme. As architects, we often talk about the city, but we have stopped taking care of it. At most, we describe it, but too often we are strangers to the dynamics that determine its form and function.

BC: Yes, but for example, the Paris metro works well and it was planned. For me, the Paris metro is a paradise: people of all colors, all social levels, compressed in a closed space, coexist well. It gives me hope every time I take it.

MV: I would say that is an excellent conclusion. Thank you.

Interview conducted by Marco Vanucci.

